

Quantum Bound Average Momentum of Zero and Special Relativity

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We have argued in previous notes that the quantum notion of \hbar/p and \hbar/E spatial and time intervals follows from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant, $A = -Et + px$. The next step is to create the dynamic probability $\exp(ipx - iEt)$. The $\exp(ipx)$ part follows from equal probability for any x in an interval 0 to \hbar/p , while $\exp(-iEt)$ enforces the notion of these intervals and a similar argument follows for $\exp(-iEt)$.

Even though $\exp(ipx)$ is an unusual complex kind of probability, its validity may be tested by analysing the 2-slit experiment etc. We discuss here, however, a consistency check with the special relativistic derivation of free particle quantum mechanics. It is possible to classically consider a rest mass as consisting of either a photon or massive particle bouncing back and forth in a little region. On average, the momentum is 0 , but if one considers $\exp(ipx)$ and an uncertainty region \hbar/p which may be of the same size, then one has an entangled state: $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$. In this case, one needs to confirm that average momentum density integrates to 0 so that the result is consistent with the average momentum obtained from the classical trajectory with equal probability for all x points. This result follows as we show. This approach also seems to explain why even for a nonrelativistic bound state, one writes $\exp(-iEnt) = \exp(-i E_n t + p_{cm} x)$ where $p_{cm}=0$ for the center-of-mass, ignoring, so to speak, the internal quantum issues. This approach treats the bound state as a localized "mass" with binding energy E_n . We thus suggest that there should be a parallel between quantum mechanics and special relativity ($-Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant) linked to the notion of rest mass.

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics and Special Relativity

We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et' + px'$, such that if x_0 , to yield an A , then $x_0 + \hbar/p$ and $t_0 + \hbar/E$ yield the same A . This Lorentz invariant is linked to the notion of a particle at rest in the rest frame because $A = -m_0 c^2 t$. From this uncertainty in x', t' one may create the dynamic probability $\exp(-iEt' + ipx')$. (Here we drop the primes on x, t .) This mathematical form may be tested by analysing the 2-slit experiment, but here we focus on checking for an internal consistency.

As noted, $A = -Et' + px' = -m_0 c^2 t$ may be used to consider the relation between a particle at rest (with mass) and one moving. This leads to the notion of \hbar/p and \hbar/E as fluctuation regions and $\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt)$ (primes dropped) as probabilities. In turn, one may consider a mass, m_0 , at rest as consisting of a photon or massive particle bouncing back and forth between two walls. On average the momentum is zero. This statement is based on considering a classical trajectory and assigning equal probability weights to each x . It was argued, however, that there should also exist a probability $\exp(ipx)$ with \hbar/p being on the order of the distance between the walls. This suggests that one must be able to calculate an average p using this $\exp(ipx)$. In particular, one has an entangled state described by:

$$W(x) = \exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Using: } \langle p \rangle = \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \{p \exp(ipx) - p \exp(-ipx)\} / \{ \exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) \} \quad ((2))$$

one may show that this integral is zero which is consistent with the trajectory approach. (The x integral runs over 0 to \hbar/p .) Here: $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents spatial density.

Extending this Idea to a Quantum Bound State

((2)) allows for a consistency check with the relativistic derivation of free particle quantum mechanics, but we argue that the ideas associated above seem to carry over to the notion of a quantum bound state. In the above section, we try to model a rest mass by a bouncing photon or particle with rest mass. This is equivalent to localizing it by a potential (for a particle with rest mass). Thus, we argue that the notions above should apply equally well to a bound quantum state, but one can no longer use $\exp(ipx)$, but must use a more general function $W(x)$. If this function is either even or odd, i.e. an eigenfunction of parity, then one is guaranteed to have the quantum average momentum equal zero for both nonrelativistic and relativistic quantum mechanics, i.e.

$$\langle p \rangle = \int dx W^*(x) (-i\hbar/dx) W(x) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

If $W(x)$ is even, then d/dx makes it odd and the integral is 0. If $W(x)$ is odd, then $W^*(x)$ is odd, but dW/dx is even leading to an overall odd function and an integral of 0. Thus, the entangled quantum state gives an average p of zero just like the classical bound state which has motion to the right followed by time reversed motion to the left which implies 0 average momentum if dt (the time spent in each dx) is proportional to probability.

As a result, if one solves the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equations to obtain E_n (energy) levels, the time portion of the wavefunction is:

$$\exp(-iE_n t) = \exp(-iE_n t + p_{cm} x) \quad \text{where } p_{cm}=0 \quad ((3))$$

The fact that a free particle is represented by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ even in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics seems to point to a special relativistic derivation of the theory or at least a link. Given that one may obtain a center-of-mass wavefunction for the bound problem shows that one may ignore (so to speak) the internal features of the bound state and only consider it as a rest mass with binding energy $-E_n$ (together with the single particle energy $m_0 c^2$). This suggests that for consistency one should consider models of rest mass in special relativity, e.g. bouncing photons or massive particles and apply $\exp(ipx)$ to them as well.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$. This leads to $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ describing probabilistic fluctuations such that there is uniform probability from 0 to \hbar/p for x and from 0 to \hbar/E for t . If this is the case, then even though there is a clear classical

trajectory for a constant speed, e.g. $x'=vt'$, nevertheless there is associated uncertainty in x' and t' (not for the trajectory), but perhaps for impulse delivery/interaction.

If this is the case, we consider models of the rest mass, m_0 , used to establish $A = -m_0 c^2 t = -Et' + px'$ in the first place. We consider either a photon or massive particle bouncing back and forth between two walls. Classically, i.e. based on the trajectory, one has an average momentum of zero. In other words, it appears as if one has a rest mass. If the distance between the walls is small, (i.e. on the order of \hbar/p), this means that $\exp(ipx)$ considerations should apply and that one has an entangled state described by $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$. This state should also have an average momentum of 0, otherwise one could not argue for a rest mass. Using ((2)), one sees that a density weighted average momentum is indeed zero and so the $\exp(ipx)$ arising from special relativity seems to be consistent with models of rest masses created by trapped bouncing photons or massive particles.

We suggest that the same reasoning applies to bound quantum particles, either nonrelativistically or relativistically. If $\exp(ipx)$ is replaced with $W(x)$, then as long as $W(x)$ is either even or odd (a parity eigenfunction), average quantum momentum is zero which is consistent with average momentum calculated classically using dt as being proportional to probability. In other words, E_n from a bound quantum problem leads to $\exp(-iE_n t + i p_{cm} x)$ where $p_{cm}=0$. One may collapse the bound problem into an $m_0 c^2$ energy together with a binding energy $-E_n$. This, however, is very similar to the approach of modeling a rest mass by a bouncing photon or massive particle and seems to point to a strong link between quantum mechanics and special relativity. (We suggest in fact that free particle quantum mechanics arises from special relativistic considerations linked to fluctuations leaving $-Et + px$ unchanged).